

CORONAVIRUS LOCKDOWN AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC IMPACT ON INDIGENT HOUSEHOLDS IN IBEWA COMMUNITY, ONELGA, RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the socioeconomic impact of coronavirus lockdown in Ibewa community, Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area, Rivers State. The socio-ecological resilience theory served as the theoretical framework while the cross-sectional design was used for the study. Both probability (stratified, simple random) and non-probability(purposive) sampling techniques were used for the sampling procedures. Quantitative (questionnaire) and qualitative (Seven focus groups) were used in gathering primary data. Also, Cronbach Alpha was used to measure the reliability of instrument(s). On the basis of data collection, twenty-two (22) respondents were randomly selected from the seven (7) household groups that were already in strata ($7 \times 22 = 154$). Data collected for the study were analyzed with univariate (mean), bivariate(chi-square) and multivariate (multinomial/linear logistics regression) statistic(s) with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 23.0. Based on analysis, the study discovered that lockdown led to human right abuse, economic hardship, deviant behavior among others. In view of these findings, the study recommended that the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs Disaster Management and Social Development should design an economic recovery plan for indigent households. Also, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control should propose a legislative framework that will curb price hike of essential commodities during disease outbreak.

Keywords: coronavirus, lockdown, indigent households, palliative, resilience, socioeconomic wellbeing

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INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus (also known as Covid-19) is rebooting the universe with massive socioeconomic adjustments to urban and rural settings. The novel virus has kept life in suspense with “stay at home” directive aimed at flattening the curve. The general chorus is “stay at home to save lives”. Lin *et al.* (2020) reported that lockdown are the severest sanctions enforced by countries plagued by Covid-19. Thus, words like social distancing, social isolation, self-isolated, self-isolating, self-isolation, self-quarantine, self-quarantined, shelter-in place, flatten the curve, elbow bump, lockdown, non-essential, ventilator, corona, disinfect, postpone, outbreak, working from home, face mask and palliative have dominated the media space. According to Adom, Adu-Mensah and Sekyere (2020), indigent groups that constitute ‘hand to mouth work culture’ will experience severe economic shock from lockdown. The vulnerability status of most households defies resilient capacities during lockdown.

It is noteworthy to emphasize that security operative under the guise of enforcing lockdown, are reportedly violating human right(s). Nigeria Covid-19 task force brutalize, intimidate and destroy goods which are the main source of income for vulnerable households on daily basis (Human Right Watch, 2020). According to Olarewaju (2020), in terms of occupational proportions from a household perspective, 41.4% of household members are self-employed, 26.5% are paid employed, 2.8% are employers of labour, 15.7% are unemployed, while 13.6% are non-active in the labour force. This implies that the lockdown order by the government will certainly impair on the economic wellbeing of majority households. This problem is further complicated with the rising rate of food shortage among indigent households. Punch News (2020), reported that it is prohibitive to buy, sell or even work during lockdown. This has led to food shortage among indigent households. It is against this backdrop that this study is armed with the challenge of investigating the socioeconomic impact of coronavirus lockdown on indigent households, with reference to Ibewa Community, that experienced lockdown with no apparent palliatives to boost the resilient capacities of indigent households.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To investigate the impact of coronavirus lockdown on human right abuse;
- To discover the economic effects of coronavirus lockdown on households;
- To find out the impact of coronavirus lockdown on deviant behaviour;
- To measure the impact of Covid-19 palliatives on households during lockdown.

STUDY HYPOTHESIS

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between Increase in price of food stuffs and Covid-19 Lockdown.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

- **Coronavirus:** This refers to a global pandemic disease that emerged in 2019. The symptoms are breathing difficulty, dry cough, tiredness, fever among others.
- **Deviant Behaviour:** These refers to acts that are socially prohibitive within a given society.

- **Palliative:** These refers to food items, pharmaceuticals, health care, cash gift and other items provided by government or non-governmental organizations with the sole aim of increasing adaptability or response of indigent households to coronavirus during lockdown.
- **Resilience:** Resilience is the capacity of individual or group to adapt or respond to unfamiliar, unexpected events and extreme shocks (Folke, 2006). It is a strategy for dealing with uncertainties, particularly the distribution of palliative to indigent/ vulnerable households during lockdown.
- **Socioeconomic:** This refers to the general wellbeing of vulnerable groups during lockdown.

THEORITICAL LITERATURE

The study anchored its argument based on socio-ecological resilience theory. Social-ecological resilience, which has its origin from the works of Holling (1973), Folke (2006) is the capacity to adapt or transform in the face of change in social-ecological systems, particularly unexpected change like coronavirus pandemic, in ways that continue to support human well-being (Chapin *et al.*, 2010; Biggs, Schlüter & Schoon, 2015). Such unexpected changes include Corona pandemic. According to Walker, Holling, Carpenter and Kinzig (2004), adaptability refers to human actions that sustain, innovate, and improve development on current pathways, while transformability is about shifting development into new pathways and even creating novel ones. It is an anthropogenic method of adapting to uncertainties in order to achieve defined objectives (Walker, Abel, Anderies & Ryan, 2009). In the same vein, it implies the ability of groups or communities to cope with external stresses and disturbances as a result of social, political and environmental changes. Furthermore, Frankenberger (2013) posits that disturbance could be a collective shock shared by a large group of people (covariate shock) or a shock experienced only within a given household or community (idiosyncratic shock). In addition, Colding and Berkes (2002) argues that changes in socio-ecological system are rather inevitable to some extent and they allow resilient possibilities to develop its capacities and reorganizing itself to match with new circumstances, hence he describe social resilience as the necessity of human systems to learn to manage by change and implies that “uncertainty and surprise are part of the game” (Folk, 2006). During the period of coronavirus lockdown, the palliatives provided by policy makers and natural support system existing among vulnerable groups can help such groups adjust positively to the pandemic and become resilient to change.

The lockdown has terribly affected and still affecting the lives of those at the grassroot, particularly rural dwellers who make ends meet on daily basis (Premium Times, 2020). Also, the provision and equitable distribution of coronavirus palliatives during lockdown will enable vulnerable citizens and dependent population to be resilient. This will help indigent household groups adjust positively to the socio-economic effects of lockdown.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional design was adopted for this study. According to Uzobo, Aboluwaji, Ayinmoro and Akhuetie (2016), research design is a blue print or structure with which research is conducted. Ajoku (2006) opined that cross sectional design is very useful in gathering data from different individuals at a given point in time. Therefore, it is economical to adopt cross sectional design in the period of coronavirus lockdown. Because, it enables the researcher to take a

cross section of the study population at once. The purposive sampling technique was used in selecting Ibewa Community, Ogba/Egbema/Ndoni Local Government Area of Rivers State. Ibewa community was selected because majority of households were indigent and not resilient to the lockdown. Furthermore, a stratified sampling technique was used to classified Ibewa community into strata, reflecting (7) seven households which are: (1) Umu-Obi, (2) Umu-Azaga, (3) Umu-Anyia, (4) Umu-Ohuo, (5) Umu-Ebulu, (6) Umu-Obii, (7) Umu-Ube. Also, simple random sampling technique was used to select the names of twenty-two (22) respondents from each household groups. The sample size becomes = 154 (22 x 7). The study sample frame comprises both male and female sexes aged 18 years and above. Quantitative data for this study was gathered using structured questionnaire while focus group schedule with the aid of recorder was used in gathering qualitative data (Uzobo, *et al.*, 2016). The questionnaire was structured on the basis of 4-point Likert measurement scale. The criterion mean is 2.50. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability of questionnaire. Qualitative data were analyzed with narrative technique. Lastly, quantitative data were analysed with mean, chi-square and linear regression with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

One hundred and fifty-four (154) copies of questionnaire were distributed to seven household groups that constitute Ibewa community. It is noteworthy that all copies of questionnaire distributed where retrieved and found valid for the study. Therefore, analysis was based on the (154=100%) retrieved copies of questionnaire and seven (7) focus groups.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Socio-Demographic Variables and Households (N=154, %=100)

Variable(s)	Household(s)							Σ	X ²	DF	P-Value
	Umu-Obi	Umu-Azaga	Umu-Anya	Umu-Ohuo	Umu-Ebulu	Umu-Obii	Umu-Ube				
	(n=42, %=27.3)	(n=25, %=16.2)	(n=10, %=6.5)	(n=11, %=7.1)	(n=42, %=27.3)	(n=14, %=9.1)	(n=10, %=6.5)	(N=154, %=100.0)			
Sex:											
Male	42(27.3)	7(4.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	23(14.9)	1(0.6)	9(5.8)	82(53.2)	84.6	6	0.000
Female	0(0.0)	18(11.7)	10(6.5)	11(7.1)	19(12.3)	13(8.4)	1(0.6)	72(46.8)			
Age:											
18-28	20(13.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(1.9)	0(0.0)	23(14.9)	220.3	18	0.000
29-38	13(8.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	8(5.2)	21(13.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	42(27.3)			
39-48	6(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	21(13.6)	11(7.1)	10(6.5)	48(31.2)			
50>	3(1.9)	25(16.2)	10(6.5)	3(1.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	41(26.6)			
Education:											
No formal education	7(4.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	10(6.5)	1(0.6)	18(11.7)	132.1	18	0.000
Primary	14(9.1)	10(6.5)	10(6.5)	11(7.1)	13(8.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	58(37.7)			
Secondary	21(13.6)	15(9.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	16(10.4)	0(0.0)	7(4.5)	59(38.3)			
Tertiary	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	13(8.4)	4(2.6)	2(1.3)	19(12.3)			

Table (1) above shows the cross-tabulation of socio-demographic characteristics and household of respondents.

Firstly, analysis proved that there is an association between sex and household of respondents (p=0.000). A breakdown of respondent's sex indicates that 82(53.2%) are male while 72(46.8%) are female. Based on this, it is clear that majority of respondents are male. Also, data collected indicate that there is an association between age and household of respondents (p=0.000). Analysis of age shows that 23(14.9%) of respondents fell within the age grade of 18-28, 42(27.3%) were aged 29-38 years, 48(31.2%) fell within the age limit of 39-48 years while 41(26.6%) of respondents were 50 years and above. Therefore, majority of respondents fell within the age bracket of 39-48 years. Furthermore, analysis revealed that there is a significant relationship between education and household of respondents (p=0.000). A breakdown of the analysis indicates that 18(11.7%) of respondents had no formal education, 58(37.7%), had primary education, 59(38.3%) had secondary education while 19(12.3%) had tertiary education.

Table 1: Cont'd

Variable(s)	Household(s)							Σ	X ²	DF	P-Value
	Umu-Obi	Umu-Azaga	Umu-Anya	Umu-Ohuo	Umu-Ebulu	Umu-Obii	Umu-Ube	(N=154, %=100.0)			
	(n=42, %=27.3)	(n=25, %=16.2)	(n=10, %=6.5)	(n=11, %=7.1)	(n=42, %=27.3)	(n=14, %=9.1)	(n=10, %=6.5)				
Average Number Per Household:											
<20	7(4.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	7(4.5)	230.1	30	0.000
21-40	15(9.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	10(6.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	25(16.2)			
41-60	20(13.0)	8(5.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(0.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	29(18.8)			
61-80	0(0.0)	17(11.0)	3(1.9)	0(0.0)	8(5.2)	1(0.6)	1(0.6)	30(19.5)			
81-100	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	7(4.5)	5(3.2)	0(0.0)	9(5.8)	2(1.3)	23(14.9)			
101>	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	6(3.9)	23(14.9)	4(2.6)	7(4.5)	40(26.0)			
Occupation:											
Farming	22(14.3)	19(12.3)	3(1.9)	0(0.0)	7(4.5)	10(6.5)	1(0.6)	62(40.30)	243.4	42	0.000
Fishing	9(5.8)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	4(2.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	13(8.4)			
Hunting	11(7.1)	6(3.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	17(11.0)			
Trading	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	7(4.5)	1(0.6)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	8(5.2)			
Civil	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(1.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	3(1.9)			
Servant	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(1.3)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(1.3)			
Unskilled											
Labourer	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	5(3.2)	29(18.8)	4(2.6)	2(1.3)	40(26.0)			
Unemployed	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	2(1.3)	0(0.0)	7(4.5)	9(5.8)			
Skilled											
Labourer											

The above table (1) indicates that there is a significant relationship between average number of respondents in each household and households ($p=0.000$). Specifically, 7(4.5%) of respondents fell within an average household of <20, 25(16.2%) are within the average of 21-40, 29(18.8%) fell within an average of 41-60, 30(19.5%) fell within the average of 61-80, 23(14.9%) are within the average of 81-100 while 40(26.0%) of respondents fell within an average household of 101> during the study. Lastly, analysis shows that occupation correlated with household group of respondents ($p=0.000$). A breakdown of occupation reveals that majority 62(40.30%) of respondents are farmers, followed by 40(26.0%) for unemployed, 17(11.0%) for hunting, 13(8.4%) for fishing, 9(5.8%) for skilled labourer, 8(5.2%) for trading, 3(1.9%) for civil servant and 2(1.3%) for unskilled labourer, This signifies that farming is the primary source of livelihood among indigent household groups in Ibewa community.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Human Right Abuse amid Covid-19 Lockdown

Human Right Abuse	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Rank	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis		
								Std. Error	Std. Error	
Lockdown defaulters are being flogged by soldiers.	154	1.00	4.00	3.3571	5	.98802	-1.099	.195	-.372	.389
Covid-19 task force are destroying the goods in market places.	154	1.00	4.00	3.3636	4	.81504	-1.422	.195	1.805	.389
Strict restriction of movement	154	1.00	4.00	3.4156	3	.62310	-.906	.195	1.400	.389
Ban on religious gathering	154	1.00	4.00	3.7143	2	.53277	-1.979	.195	4.539	.389
Police brutality	154	1.00	4.00	3.7987	1	.47664	-2.737	.195	9.091	.389
Valid N (listwise)	154									

Based on the criterion mean=2.50, table (2) above revealed high rate of human right abuse in the research locale within the period covered by the study. A focus group discussion with participants reveals thus:

“They stopped us from going to market but they can’t give us what to eat” FGD2/Umu-Obi Household.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Economic Effects of Covid-19 Lockdown

Economic Effects Of Covid-19 lockdown	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Rank	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis		
								Std. Error	Std. Error	
Trading activities have been affected	154	1.00	4.00	3.1883	7	.75641	-.788	.195	.532	.389
Market are closed due to Covid-19	154	1.00	4.00	3.4805	6	.63884	-1.145	.195	1.591	.389
Hike in price of foods stuffs	154	1.00	4.00	3.4935	5	.58574	-1.062	.195	2.240	.389
Barber shops have been affected	154	1.00	4.00	3.5649	4	.60418	-1.424	.195	2.731	.389
There is increasing food shortage	154	1.00	4.00	3.6169	3	.63861	-2.050	.195	5.244	.389
Motor cycling activities have been affected	154	1.00	4.00	3.6818	2	.53265	-1.692	.195	3.520	.389
Job loss	154	1.00	4.00	3.7338	1	.59455	-2.486	.195	6.362	.389
Valid N (listwise)	154									

Table (3) above shows the negative economic impact of the pandemic on indigent households within the period covered by the study. A focus group discussion with participants reveals thus:

“We find it difficult to feed during lockdown, because our foodstuffs are finished” FGD4/Umu Ebulu Household.

Further probing by researcher revealed a consensus assertion from focus group participants as thus:

“How can we feed our children when we stay at home and don't go to work” FGD5/Umu-Obii Household.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Deviant Behaviour During Covid-19 Lockdown

Deviant Behavior during Covid-19 Lockdown	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Rank	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis		
								Std. Error	Std. Error	
People steal to eat due to high price of foodstuffs	154	1.00	4.00	2.9416	5	1.09208	-.646	.195	-.911	.389
Crime rate is increasing during lockdown	154	1.00	4.00	3.2662	4	.90779	-1.298	.195	1.011	.389
There is pocket of violence during lockdown	154	1.00	4.00	3.4221	3	.62395	-.927	.195	1.418	.389
Foodstuffs provided by government can't feed a household	154	1.00	4.00	3.5000	2	.61835	-1.176	.195	1.944	.389
There is increase in petty theft now compared to pre-lockdown.	154	1.00	4.00	3.6558	1	.61972	-1.949	.195	3.975	.389
Valid N (listwise)	154									

Based on the criterion mean=2.50, table (4) above revealed high rate of deviant behaviour in the research locale within the period covered by the study. A focus group discussion with participants reveals thus:

“We are now experiencing cassava theft in our farmland” FGD/6/Umu-Ube Household.

In the same vein, a focus group discussion with participants drawn from Umu-Ohuo household reveals that:

“Hunger virus makes people to steal foodstuffs not coronavirus” FGD/7/Umu-Ohuo Household.

Table 5: Cross-Tabulation* Covid-19 Palliative* Household

Covid-19 Palliative(s) ^a	B	Std. Error	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Rice/Yam/ Indomie	Intercept	.693	1.225	.320	1	.571		
	Umu-Obi	21.748	11520.144	.000	1	.998	2786982698 .604	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Azaga	21.748	14931.813	.000	1	.999	2786982698 .604	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Anyaa	21.748	8923.458	.000	1	.998	2786982698 .604	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Ohuo	21.748	8508.183	.000	1	.998	2786982698 .604	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Ebulu	21.684	11432.834	.000	1	.998	2614196106 .671	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Obii	1.609	1.612	.996	1	.318	5.000	.212 117.894
Beans/Garri/ Spagethi	Umu-Ube	0 ^c	.	.	0	.	.	.
	Intercept	.000	1.414	.000	1	1.000		
	Umu-Obi	1.099	13302.313	.000	1	1.000	3.000	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Azaga	1.099	17241.768	.000	1	1.000	3.000	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Anyaa	1.099	.000	.	1	.	3.000	3.000 3.000
	Umu-Ohuo	1.099	.000	.	1	.	3.000	3.000 3.000
	Umu-Ebulu	19.382	11432.834	.000	1	.999	261419610. 667	.000 . ^b
Tomatoes /Onion/ Pepper	Umu-Obii	1.099	1.826	.362	1	.547	3.000	.084 107.447
	Umu-Ube	0 ^c	.	.	0	.	.	.
	Intercept	1.792	1.080	2.752	1	.097		
	Umu-Obi	-.693	13302.313	.000	1	1.000	.500	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Azaga	-.693	17241.768	.000	1	1.000	.500	.000 . ^b
	Umu-Anyaa	-.693	.000	.	1	.	.500	.500 .500
	Umu-Ohuo	-.693	.000	.	1	.	.500	.500 .500
Umu-Ebulu	-.693	13201.501	.000	1	1.000	.500	.000 . ^b	
Umu-Obii	-	.000	.	1	.	9.603E-10	9.603 E-10 9.603E-10	
Umu-Ube	20.764	0 ^c	.	0	.	.	.	

In table (5) above, Covid-19 palliatives were used to cross-tabulate with households. Analysis returned a zero correlation. This shows that Covid-19 palliatives distributed by government had no impact on indigent household groups during lockdown.

Figure 1: Estimated Income of Households During Lockdown

Figure 1 above, shows a very low income of household groups during coronavirus lockdown. Das and Sanchez-Paramo (2020) concurs that staying at home as a result of lockdown restriction is not a pleasant option as it only subjects indigent households to harsh living conditions.

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between Increase in price of food stuffs and Covid-19 Lockdown.

Table 6: Summary of Regression Analysis Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.687 ^a	.472	.469	.42699	.472	135.925	1	152	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Covid-19 Lockdown

b. Dependent Variable: Increase in price of foodstuffs among households

Table 6 above summarizes regression results. The results indicated that there is a positive correlation between lockdown and increase in price of food stuff. In the regression statistics $r=0.687$, while $R^2=0.472$. It means that the independent variable (lockdown) explained 47.2% variation from the expected and actual results of the dependent variable (price of food stuffs). This indicates a good fit of the regression equation. Thus, there is an accurate reflection that price of food stuffs is influenced by lockdown. The more the government increase number of lockdown days, the more the price of food stuffs skyrocket.

Table 7: Test of Significance

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.721	.156		11.040	.000	1.413	2.029
	Covid-19 Lockdown	.523	.045	.687	11.659	.000	.434	.612

a. Dependent Variable: Increase in price of foods stuffs

The test of significance results, as presented in table 7 above, shows that $t=11.659$, with $df=153$ and p -value ($0.000 < 0.05$). It indicates that at 5% level of significance there is enough evidence that the regression equation is well-specified that a significant relationship between lockdown and price of food stuffs exists. Based on the findings we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that lockdown has a significant influence on price of food stuffs. We are 95% confident that the slope of the actual regression line is somewhere between 0.434 and 0.612. In other words, we are 95% sure that easing lockdown will influence price of foods stuffs between 0.434 and 0.612.

DISCUSSION

Firstly, the study has shown various forms of human right abuse experienced by respondents/participants during lockdown. The Nigerian Police Force, Military Officers and Covid-19 Task Force were reportedly brutalizing citizens who went to nearby market to buy and sell. The lockdown order made it impossible for most indigent household groups to observe their religious obligations. The study corroborates with Ozil and Aru (2010), that lockdown led to ban on non-essential business activities, closing down educational institutions, and encouraging working from home with essential service providers running on minimal operations. A focus group participant from Umu-Obi household suggested that Covid-19 task force has destroyed her goods worth #8,000. Another participant suggested that police officers were extorting traders that violated the lockdown order. Due to increasing economic hardship, it became impossible for indigent households to stay at home (Adom *eta I.* 2020). Thus, leading to altercation with police, soldiers and Covid-19 task force on daily basis.

Secondly, the study has shown the economic challenges associated with the lockdown. The study has shown low income status for indigent households during lockdown. Result has also shown that vulnerable households experienced food shortage. This affirms the United Nation World Food Programme (2020) report that lockdown could nearly double the number of people around the world facing acute hunger. A focus group participant suggested that lockdown grinded all farming activities. According to the study, farming is the major occupation of indigent households. Thus, the lockdown conflicted with their major source of livelihood. International Energy Agency (2020) also predicted a negative impact of lockdown on global economies. In the market, traders were taking undue advantage of lockdown to hike the price of essential commodities. A focus group participant suggested that a basin of garri (cassava flour) that was sold at #4,000 before the lockdown was sold at #12,000 during lockdown. This corroborated

with the findings of Adom *eta I.* (2020) that during lockdown, most traders took undue advantage by increasing the price of foods stuffs. There was also job loss, because farming which served as the dominant occupation of indigent households was put to hold (Liu, Zhou & Li, 2020; Lin et al., 2020; WHO, 2019).

Thirdly, there were new forms of deviance behaviour during lockdown. A focus group participant suggested that in “Akabuka market” a female trader fought a police officer. This was because the trader insisted on selling her goods during lockdown. The study has also shown how lockdown led to anomie as conceptualized by Merton (1965). This is in relation to the ban on human and vehicular movement which affected farming occupation of indigent households. Another focus group participant suggested that they have never witnessed this kind of hardship where thieves go to farmland in daylight to harvest cassava and sell in the market.

Finally, the study has shown that Covid- 19 palliatives provided by government are beans, yams, rice, noodles, pepper, onion, spaghetti and etcetera. However, a focus group participant suggested that they received just little foods stuffs. Another focus group participant responded that in a family of seven, they received just two noddle (s) and two cups of rice as Covid-19 palliatives. This affirms the finding of Azumah (2020) that there were unfair distribution of food and grocery packages by the government to their party members during lockdown.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs Disaster Management and Social Development (FMHDS) should design an economic recovery plan for indigent households that lost their source of income during lockdown. This will help to cushion the economic effects of the lockdown and enhance general resilience. Also, the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) should fashion a legislative framework that will monitor human right abuse, police brutality and regulate price of essential commodities during disease outbreak. Kahneman, Knetsch, and Thaler (1986) recommend public condemnation and shaming of companies that callously profiteer citizens through surge pricing during emergencies. These approaches when adopted by the Nigerian government would ensure that the indigent households will be resilient to economic hardship associated with future lockdown.

LIMITATION

The researcher (s) experienced challenges in visiting the head of households to seek for consent before the field work. This was due to the ban on movement (shelter - in place) during lockdown.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated coronavirus lockdown and socio-economic impact on indigent households. The study has shown that lockdown led to human right abuse (s), as goods belonging to indigent traders were destroyed by Covid-19 task force. The study also revealed key factors that made it difficult for indigent households to cope with lockdown. Also, the study has shown how lockdown led to food shortage, increase in price of foods stuffs among others. Thus, leading to new forms of deviant behaviour. It was shown how pocket of violence and theft increased during lockdown. In recognition of zero resilient capacity of indigent households, Nigerian government chose to cushion the economic effects of lockdown by distributing Covid-19 palliative. The study has also shown how indigent households benefited

minimally from Covid-19 palliatives due to unnecessary political interference and challenges involved in accessing the palliatives. Therefore, the study conclude that indigent households have minimal resilient capacity during lockdown.

CONFLICT OF INTREST DISCLOSURE

The author (s) declares that there are no conflicts of interest. This work is solely the intellectual property of the researchers to investigate the socio-economic impact of coronavirus lockdown on indigent households.

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